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Smart Blue-Green Infrastructure for Urban Climate Resilience: A Conceptual Synthesis Framework

Sara Rahmani*

1. Master of Landscape Architecture, Shiraz University, Iran, sararahmanib@gmail.com

Abstract

Climate-related extremes are becoming increasingly severe in urban areas, and blue-green infrastructure (BGI) has been widely recognized as a practical approach for strengthening urban climate resilience. The integration of smart technologies with BGI systems may further improve climate-responsive urban management through more informed, adaptive, and context-sensitive approaches. This study explores the relationship between smartness orientations and climate-resilience functions in urban environments, with a particular focus on resilience to heat, floods, and droughts. Through a synthesis review of literature on Smart BGI, smartness orientations, and climate-resilience functions, an analytical mapping framework was developed. The analytical mapping indicates that monitoring has the strongest association with all reviewed resilience functions and remains the most extensively studied orientation. Predictive approaches are more commonly linked to flood resilience, responsive-control approaches to thermal and flood resilience, and adaptive management to drought resilience. Decision-support approaches demonstrate a moderate relevance across all resilience functions. The study further highlights the importance of considering contextual conditions and operational limitations in the design and implementation of Smart BGI. Enhancing the resilience contribution of smart BGI should therefore extend beyond technological integration and monitoring alone toward better alignment with the ecological and hydrological functions of BGI systems, as well as more adaptive and multifunctional resilience strategies across diverse urban contexts.

Keywords: Blue-green infrastructure, Smart technologies, Climate resilience, Nature-based solutions

1. Introduction

Urban areas are particularly vulnerable to climate-related extremes, such as droughts, floods, and heat waves, because over half of the global population currently resides in urban areas, and this proportion continues to increase. Moreover, urban areas intensify climate change impacts due to a dense built environment and concentrated socio-economic activities [1]. Cities suffer from the "urban heat island" (UHI) effect (the phenomenon whereby cities appear to be warmer than the surrounding rural area), which generates serious inconveniences

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for the most vulnerable citizens, especially the elderly and children [2]. Additionally, high impervious surface coverage in urban areas can intensify both flood and drought risks by increasing surface runoff and reducing groundwater recharge [3, 4]. Therefore, implementation of strategies that address the consequences of climate change is essential.

Actions to address climate change and its effects on society and the environment are oriented in two directions: mitigation, to progressively reduce emissions of climate-changing gases responsible for global warming, and adaptation, to reduce the vulnerability of environmental, social, and economic systems and to increase their capacity for climate resilience. Many adaptation and mitigation options can help address climate change, but no single option is sufficient by itself [2]. Nature-based solutions (NBS) are measures inspired and powered by nature that simultaneously provide environmental, societal, and economic benefits while helping mitigate climate change effects and build resilience [5]. In order to integrate nature-based solutions into urban development projects, the share of green and blue areas is required as a basic indicator [6]. Blue-Green Infrastructure (BGI) is seen as a subset of NBS [7]. A vast number of studies have focused on BGI as a resilience strategy.

BGI systems are able to combine natural and semi-natural systems with engineered solutions to address urban water management, climate adaptation, biodiversity, and human well-being. It emphasizes the integration of water bodies (rivers, lakes, wetlands) and green spaces (parks, gardens, green roofs) to create multifunctional urban landscapes. These infrastructures provide multiple ecosystem services such as flood mitigation, air quality improvement, urban cooling, and recreational spaces. BGI systems can also support the natural water cycle by enhancing infiltration, evapotranspiration, and groundwater recharge, which are often disrupted in heavily urbanized areas [8]. On the other hand, conventional BGI approaches may lack robustness under extreme climate conditions. The blue-green water integration has limited capacity to mitigate storm sewer overflow and may not be sufficient to significantly reduce flood risk [9]. Additionally, more greenery raises water demand during droughts due to higher evapotranspiration [10]. Therefore, unregulated implementation of BGI might lead to unintended outcomes, as it can be affected by various factors including water availability, tree traits, urban morphology, and climate conditions [7-9, 11].

Various strategies have been proposed to strengthen the role of BGI in urban climate resilience, including its integration with grey infrastructure, planting drought-tolerant species, and the incorporation of smart technologies for monitoring, prediction, decision-making, and adaptive control [7, 12]. Smart BGI has been discussed through sensors, real-time monitoring, IoT, AI, machine learning, digital twins, predictive modelling, and adaptive management [6, 12, 13]. While smart BGI approaches have been considerably discussed in areas such as stormwater management, real-time irrigation control, and environmental monitoring, their contribution to broader urban climate resilience functions remains fragmented and insufficiently articulated across the literature.

Much of the existing studies focus on specific smart technologies, pilot projects, or individual performance domains, while less attention has been paid to how different smartness orientations are associated with diverse climate resilience functions within urban BGI. Although the relevance of smartness orientations may vary across different contextual conditions including climate, urban morphology, infrastructure capacity, governance, data availability, and maintenance resources [11, 13, 14], there remains a need for a conceptual

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synthesis that maps how smartness orientations have been linked to resilience functions and clarifies under which these links may be meaningful in the literature.

In response, this paper develops a conceptual synthesis of smart BGI for enhancing urban climate resilience by examining how different forms of smartness orientations, including monitoring, predictive, decision-support, responsive, and adaptive orientations, can contribute to urban climate resilience functions, including resilience to drought, urban heat, and flood. This study aims to clarify the conceptual links between smart orientations and climate resilience functions in the literature, explore their integrated operational role in smart BGI, and discuss conditions and limitations of smart BGI in enhancing urban climate resilience.

2. Smartness in BGI for Urban Climate Resilience

In this section, an analytical synthesis of reviewed smartness orientations used for enhancing urban climate resilience is presented. The reviewed literature suggests the following smartness orientations within smart BGI systems:

2.1 Monitoring-Oriented Smartness

In several BGI studies, sensing and, in particular, real-time monitoring have been used to generate continuous environmental observations and data that can inform the assessment of BGI functional behavior in relation to urban climate resilience. The findings of these monitoring-oriented studies provide an empirical basis for understanding the performance, efficiency and real-world functioning of BGI systems. For instance, in a study in Singapore, a network of meteorological sensors was used to assess radiative cooling of a tropical urban park and identified tree height and density as effective factors on the park cool island effect in that specific context [15]. Smart sensors that are part of GI can keep track of variables like soil moisture, temperature, and pollution levels, making it feasible for on-the-spot irrigation and quick reactions to poor conditions [13]. Overall, monitoring provides the observational basis upon which further smartness orientations can be developed.

2.2 Predictive Smartness

Environmental management involves increasingly complex challenges related to resource allocation, urban development, and climate resilience. Predictive analytical approaches can support stakeholders by anticipating environmental changes, identifying potential risks, and improving resource management through data-driven insights [1]. Smartness can go beyond mere environmental sensing toward predictive control approaches. Predictive models can identify and extract significant trends from the cleaned and processed data, uncover patterns hidden in the raw data through advanced data science algorithms, and promote timely responses [16].

A study conducted by Al Mehedi et al. compared a deep learning-based predictive model (LSTM) neural network with two traditional models to predict the recession of ponded water depth in a rain garden, and observed the performance of the suggested models for continuous recession rate time series and specific storms. This study showed that the LSTM predictive model integrated with machine learning and deep learning tools outperformed conventional simulations in prediction [17].

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2.3 Decision-Support Smartness

Some studies have expanded the use of smart technologies in BGIs to enhance climate resilience, which enables detailed analysis, prioritization, thorough evaluation, and risk management. These technologies can assist in the decision-making process through linking data and modelling outputs to planning, maintenance, and management decisions; without this link, smartness may remain informational rather than operational [18, 19]. A good example is the research by Visan et al., which proposes an intelligent decision-support system (DSS) for the management of green-blue infrastructure. The study emphasizes using real-time multi-user DSS tools in a collaborative environment where stakeholders can work together to make informed decisions to improve overall GBI performance, and a mixed use of dashboard-type, collaborative, and crowdsourcing applications was recommended to avoid results distortions [20]. AI, as a smart tool, can play a significant role in facilitating the decision-making process. By interpreting environmental data in real-time, AI can guide decision-making processes and set priorities for interventions, leading to the successful execution of green infrastructure initiatives [13].

2.4 Responsive Control Smartness

In this study, responsive control refers to the ability of a system to modify and regulate its operation in response to real-time environmental conditions through controlled actions, rather than solely through monitoring, prediction, or decision-support [16, 21]. Zhou et al. studied a smart BGI equipped with sensors and electronically movable gates that was actuated by both rule-based control (RBC) and model predictive control (MPC) algorithms. This method enabled initiating runoff detention and automatic pre-discharge during the most vulnerable period of peak storm intensity [22].

2.5 Adaptive Smartness

In this paper, adaptive smartness in BGI is understood as the continuous monitoring and refinement of operational or management strategies through real-time environmental feedback and dynamic system adjustment based on learning from previous experiences under changing environmental conditions. Depending on system complexity, adaptive approaches may also incorporate other smartness orientations [13, 23, 24].

This analytical progression provides a conceptual basis for examining how different smartness orientations may support resilience-related functions in Smart BGI systems. In this context, smartness should not be understood merely as a single-purpose technological feature or digital addition to BGI. Instead, it can be viewed as a set of operational capabilities that may support resilience through different functional pathways under changing environmental conditions.

Table 1 provides a literature-based overview of smartness orientations supporting climate resilience in smart BGI. It should be noted that each orientation presented in Table 1 is interpreted according to its dominant operational role within BGI systems and does not represent a fixed classification framework. The boundaries between presented orientations may overlap.

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Table 1: Overview of smartness orientations supporting climate resilience in smart BGI

Number	Smartness orientation	Capability	Sample enabling tools and technologies	Primary role
1	Monitoring-oriented	Monitoring and sensing	Geospatial monitoring platforms, environmental sensors, IoT systems, UAV imagery, and NDVI	Performance observation and increasing environmental awareness
2	Predictive	Forecasting and modelling	Predictive environmental modelling tools including ML-based forecasting approaches	Anticipation and preparedness
3	Decision-support	Analytical evaluation, prioritization, and planning support	AI, GIS, scenario modelling, digital twins, dashboards, and assessment platforms	Operational guidance to make informed decisions
4	Responsive-control	Real-time operational control	Smart valves, real-time and rule-based control systems, smart mist spray, smart irrigation controller, and automated drainage system	Immediate operational response
5	Adaptive	Feedback-informed, self-organization and dynamic adjustment	Dynamic maintenance, feedback loops, adaptive control algorithms, and learning-based optimization	Continuous refinement and adaptive management

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3. Climate-Resilience Functions in Smart BGI

In this study, resilience to heat, flood, and drought is examined as the primary analytical focus, as these hazards consistently emerge among the most recurrent climate-related stressors in the reviewed studies. To maintain a consistent analytical structure, each climate resilience function is discussed in terms of the BGI function involved, the supporting smartness orientations, and the pathway through which it supports resilience-related performance.

3.1 Heat and Thermal Resilience

The combination of urbanization and global warming leads to urban overheating and compounds the frequency and intensity of extreme heat events due to climate change [25]. Urban areas are frequently warmer than non-urban surroundings, known as the urban heat island (UHI) effect, while blue and green spaces are defined as cool island (CI) areas because they are conducive to alleviating UHI. [15]. Recent studies demonstrated that while fragmented green spaces provide only localized cooling effects, well-connected green-blue networks can link multiple cooling sources within 200–500 m, thereby amplifying regional cooling [14]. Green infrastructures contribute to climate resilience by reducing land surface temperature (LST) and surface urban heat island (SUHI) through shading, evapotranspiration, thermal insulation, and sun radiation blockage [26], while blue infrastructure, which includes water bodies such as ponds, canals, rivers, streams, lakes, and wetlands, absorbs heat and cools the surrounding area through evaporation [25].

A study by Li et al. focused on how BGI affects heat resilience under varying microclimatological conditions in six different climate zones in Africa. In this study, satellite imagery (Landsat-8) was used for monitoring purposes by extracting Land Surface Temperature (LST) and Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI). The cloud-based tool Local Climate Zone (LCZ) generator was used for assessment and classification of various climate zones. GIS enabled spatial planning and facilitated decision-making [27].

Another study by Jang et al. focused on the psychological aspect of outdoor thermal comfort of pedestrians at a city-wide scale. In this study, UMEP-derived SVFs, Landsat 8-derived LST, and SDOT urban big data monitoring sensor-interpolated T_a were considered as key inputs for estimating cooling effects of BGI [28]. Numerous studies have approved the effectiveness of mist spray systems in cooling and increasing humidity in urban space; Wang et al. further developed this system by proposing a smart system that can alleviate heat stress through networking and controlling the mist spray system, temperature sensor, and body recognition devices. This interactive system is designed to be responsive and efficiently create cool spots [29]. Such systems may operate more efficiently when integrated with GI. Mist spray systems have been shown to perform better under shaded environments [30], and the cooling effect of GI is due to natural evapotranspiration capacity [23, 31]. This integration highlights the potential of combining mist spray systems with shade-providing vegetation to enhance localized thermal resilience.

Overall, smart technologies have increasingly facilitated responsive approaches for enhancing thermal resilience at microclimate scales. However, additional measures should still be taken to generate more advanced adaptive solutions applicable on a broader urban scale.

3.2 Flood Resilience

Research has shown that the intensity and frequency of heavy precipitation events have increased since the 1950s over most land areas with sufficient observations. Anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions are likely the main driver behind this observed trend [32]. In addition, urban areas face increasing flood risks due to high impervious surface coverage. During periods of intense rainfall, the natural processes of infiltration and evapotranspiration are significantly hindered, resulting in rapid increases in surface runoff. This, in turn, amplifies the risk of urban flooding. Traditional flood management approaches based on gray infrastructure are increasingly showing their limitations [3]. The complexity of urban water problems means that stormwater management must solve multi-objective problems [33].

Various strategies, including BGI, were introduced to increase flood resilience and manage stormwater more efficiently. Smart responsive-control capabilities through BGIs are particularly applicable in stormwater management, as they can support both immediate and gradual regulation of water storage and runoff discharge before or during torrential rainfall and reduce overflow pressure on water management grey infrastructure like urban drainage systems and water storage facilities [22, 34]. In addition, real-time monitoring and precipitation forecast tools combined with responsive strategies can amplify the application of BGIs in water management. As Hamidiaala et al. discussed, real-time control (RTC) integration with blue-green roof systems, using specifically forecast-based control strategies involving smart, adjustable valves, has demonstrated significantly better rainfall capture in comparison with conventionally designed, passive systems [34].

Overall, the reviewed studies demonstrate the potential of all smartness capabilities within BGI systems to support flood resilience and runoff management, with monitoring, predictive, and responsive smartness appearing to be the most extensively applied orientations, whereas adaptive smartness remains comparatively less developed in terms of operational application.

3.3 Drought Resilience

Up to 55 million people suffer from drought each year [35]. As cities expand, impervious surfaces multiply, disrupting the natural hydrological cycle, intensifying surface runoff during floods, and reducing groundwater recharge, leading to droughts [4]. Drought resilience can be enhanced through multiple BGI-related pathways, including improved water storage and retention capacity, alongside the regulation of temperature and solar radiation to moderate thermal conditions and reduce evaporative water loss [25, 35].

In addition to grey infrastructure designed for water collection and storage, BGI can contribute to drought resilience through complementary green and blue functions. Green components may enhance water retention, regulate soil moisture, and provide thermal buffering, while blue elements such as ponds, wetlands, and retention basins can store water and help sustain local moisture conditions during dry periods [35, 36-38].

Rather than only reducing stress on BGI elements under dry conditions, smart capabilities can strengthen the role of BGI in drought resilience by adaptive water retention, storage, reuse, and allocation that support efficient water management [38, 39]. For instance, green roofs operated by real-time control can retain water for an extended duration by closing a control valve, which enhances the heat reduction impact and generates anaerobic zones for

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water treatment. To address drought-related environmental impacts through BGI systems, maintaining plant health and ensuring BGI maintenance are essential. For this purpose, the Internet of Things (IoT) technology can be leveraged for tasks such as monitoring soil conditions or adaptive irrigating plants [40]. A water management system in Barcelona leverages IoT to optimize water usage using a network of sensors to monitor water consumption, detect leaks in real-time, and manage irrigation systems efficiently. This approach has led to significant water savings and improved resource management [4].

To reuse water during droughts, infiltration is required. In a study by Lopes et al., the implementation of a comprehensive monitoring and decision-support system that captures and processes data from various sensors and devices transformed the wastewater treatment process significantly. In this study, a Distributed Control System (DCS) is responsible for the monitoring, control, and actuation of the sensor network, pumps, and the renewable energy system. This DCS relies greatly on microcontrollers, microprocessors, sensors, and actuators. Sensors gather critical incoming information from the process; at the same time, microcontrollers receive, process, and send the sensor data to an in-house developed cloud platform (MRIPTA). When the need arises, the microcontrollers operate the actuators. This smart responsive capability can facilitate water reuse during dry conditions [41].

While responsive capabilities can support drought resilience, adaptive approaches may further complement smart systems given the gradual and evolving nature of drought conditions. Unlike storms and floods, which often necessitate immediate responses, drought processes typically develop over longer timescales and require continuous adjustment to changing environmental conditions [42-44].

Based on a qualitative synthesis of the reviewed literature, Figure 1 represents the relative strength of conceptual associations between smartness orientations and the three core climate resilience functions. The strength of each conceptual link is interpreted based on three considerations: The operational role of each orientation, the nature of the climate-related hazard, and the prominence of the relationship in the reviewed literature. This diagram reflects that smartness does not generate a single resilience effect; rather, different smartness orientations may support resilience-related functions through different operational pathways in smart BGI, depending on the type of climate resilience function involved. Figure 1 is intended as an analytical interpretation, not a fixed taxonomy. Each smartness orientation may perform different operational roles in addressing different climate-related hazards. For instance, monitoring approaches can support thermal assessment in thermal resilience applications, while also functioning as soil moisture sensing systems in drought management. According to the reviewed literature, some smartness orientations appear to be more strongly associated with specific climate resilience functions within smart BGI systems.

The analytical mapping presented in Figure 1 indicates that monitoring has a strong association with all reviewed climate resilience functions, including thermal, flood, and drought resilience. Predictive orientation shows a strong association with flood resilience. Decision-support orientation demonstrates a moderate association across all climate resilience functions, while responsive-control approaches have a stronger association with thermal and flood resilience due to the immediate need for timely responses during such extreme events. In contrast, adaptive management appears to have particular operational relevance for drought resilience improvement, which may be related to the gradual and evolving nature of drought conditions.

Figure 1: Summary mapping of smartness orientations across climate resilience functions and their operational roles in smart BGI

3.4 Cross-Functional Resilience and Co-benefits

Floods, droughts, and heatwaves may originate from interconnected climatic and hydrological processes rather than entirely separate climate-related extremes [35, 45, 46]. Additionally, given the multi-functionality of BGI, applying smart capabilities into BGI can contribute to different resilient functions simultaneously [35]. For instance, smart constructed wetlands may facilitate both drought and flood resilience or extend beyond climatic resilience as they may help foster climate and biodiversity resilience, leading to enhanced environmental quality in urban settings [47, 48].

Sophisticated data analytics can monitor the performance of urban green areas in air purification and carbon capture, providing instantaneous responses for policy modifications. As an example, employing satellite imagery along with urban heat mapping allows planners to identify regions that would most benefit from expanded tree canopies or green roofing solutions. This anticipatory methodology not only amplifies ecological advantages but also fosters social equity by ensuring that marginalized communities secure access to healthier surroundings [13]. Overall, in addition to the mentioned climate resilience functions, smart BGI may also generate broader resilience co-benefits, including air and water quality improvement, biodiversity enhancement, and economic and psychological benefits [35, 48, 49].

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4. Discussion

4.1 Conditions for Effective Smart BGI Performance

Smart BGI can contribute substantially to urban climate resilience; however, without appropriately integrated smart capabilities, it may also generate unintended consequences [6]. This can be seen in dense vegetation, which may enhance cooling capacity and thermal comfort, while simultaneously increasing water demand under prolonged dry conditions [7]. In this context, smartness in BGI should not be confined to environmental sensing and data collection alone, but may also facilitate more responsive, adaptive, and function-oriented management approaches.

Smart BGI is likely to perform more effectively when smart capabilities are operationally aligned with the ecological and hydrological functions of BGI through environmental assessment, predictive modelling, optimized resource allocation, responsive interventions, and adaptive management strategies [8, 50]. Its performance may further be shaped by contextual factors such as urban morphology, climatic conditions, ecological characteristics, governance structures, infrastructural capacity, and long-term maintenance [9-11]. Accordingly, the resilience potential of Smart BGI should be understood not merely through the integration of digital technologies, but through the extent to which these technologies can reinforce the functional performance of BGI systems under climate-related stresses in various contexts.

4.2 Limitations of Smart BGIs in Enhancing Climate Resilience Functions

Smartness can optimize BGI performance, but cannot replace the underlying ecological and hydrological capacities through which BGI delivers climate resilience functions [12, 13]. Additional limitations may emerge from a lack of reliable IoT communication systems and available or sufficiently accurate data, various types of data and technical complexity, as well as limited transparency in the decision-making process, which can increase uncertainty and lead to less reliable analytical outcomes [6, 12]. Moreover, security aspects to prevent cyber attacks and ethical management of information should be considered [13, 33].

Notably, approaches optimized for particular climate conditions may become potentially problematic or less suitable when applied in different environmental contexts. For example, the performance of evaporative cooling systems may be substantially reduced in humid climates, where high atmospheric moisture limits evaporative cooling efficiency [51]. A BGI element may strengthen one climate resilience function, while to some extent disrupting another. A relevant example is wetland vegetation, which may hinder desilting and sludge excavation processes and potentially obstruct water purification efforts. Accordingly, smart BGI implementation should be guided by context-specific assessment, maintenance capacity, and clear mechanisms for translating data into action, so that potential trade-offs can be identified and managed before they undermine system performance [48].

4.3 Future Directions

A considerable body of research has already focused on monitoring-based smart applications in BGI systems. Nevertheless, continued efforts are required to improve the data optimization process, model calibration and validation, and sensor and predictive modelling accuracy to reduce uncertainty in environmental assessments and operational outputs. Future developments should also ensure the algorithms are designed in a more transparent and

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unbiased manner while accounting for diverse environmental conditions and stakeholder groups. More long-term and context-sensitive investigations are needed to evaluate the performance, reliability, and adaptability of existing adaptive smart BGI systems under changing climatic conditions and over extended operational periods. Furthermore, greater attention should be directed toward potential trade-offs among different resilience functions and operational objectives.

Future research should focus on advancing action-oriented and more adaptive technologies tailored for BGI systems and further explore how smart BGI systems can be designed and implemented as multifunctional infrastructures capable of simultaneously addressing broader and more integrated dimensions of urban resilience.

5. Conclusion

This study highlights urban smart BGI as an emerging approach that integrates the multifunctional capacities of BGI with data-informed, responsive, and adaptive forms of urban climate resilience. The main contribution of this review lies in framing smart BGI through operational relationships between smartness orientations, BGI functions, and climate-related hazards. The reviewed literature suggests that smartness should not be interpreted as the presence of technology, but rather as a context-sensitive tool to lead operational roles dynamically and more accurately in climate resilience enhancement.

The synthesis of the reviewed literature also indicates that smart BGI systems do not necessarily contribute to climate resilience through a single pathway. In heat-related applications, smart capabilities are more closely associated with monitoring, spatial assessment, and responsive control. In flood-related applications, their role is mainly connected to monitoring, anticipation, and responsive control, while in drought-related applications, they are more linked to monitoring and adaptive management.

Ultimately, the long-term significance of smart BGI within urban settings lies beyond the mere integration of smart technologies. Future progress in urban smart BGI will likely depend on the extent to which smart technologies can be effectively integrated with the long-term ecological, hydrological, and operational dynamics of BGI systems, while accounting for contextual conditions and infrastructure capacity to support more informed, responsive, and adaptive approaches to climate resilience.

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